

ENGINEERING-GEOLOGICAL ZONING OF THE SOUTHERN PART OF THE KARAKALPAK USTYURT TERRITORY BASED ON RESISTANCE TO TECHNOGENIC IMPACTS

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Abstract. *The article presents data on the engineering and geological zoning of the Southern part of Ustyurt. The traditional method of mapping engineering and geological zoning has been chosen, with the allocation of taxonomic units based on well-known criteria for assessing the degree of suitability for construction or national economic development. The authors have identified four districts and 10 sites with a degree of resistance to man-made impacts and an increase in seismic intensity depending on the engineering and geological conditions of a particular site.*

Keywords: *Ustyurt, geotechnical, Karabaursky swell, Aibogirsky uplift, Kaplankyrsky plateau, Kaplankyrsky chink, Sarykamysh trough.*

Introduction. The intensive development of the Ustyurt Plateau, particularly active in recent decades, along with the specific morphometric and geological conditions of the territory, has led to the intensification and activation of hazardous exogenous geological processes that affect the stability of the geological environment. Studying the dynamics, mechanisms, factors, and patterns of these geological processes for the purpose of predicting their development and assessing their hazards is impossible without a high-quality evaluation of the engineering-geological conditions of the study area.

The high anthropogenic pressure in the region necessitates the use of modern methods of engineering-geological mapping, incorporating geographic information systems (GIS) for a comprehensive analysis of the area's engineering-geological conditions. This, in turn, can serve as a basis for predicting changes and substantiating the geocological aspects of engineering-geological zoning.

Engineering-geological zoning is the identification, within a complex and multifaceted geological environment, of territorial units characterized by common engineering-geological features, based on theoretical frameworks and methodological approaches. It involves

distinguishing these zones from others lacking such features, followed by their classification, mapping, and description [7,8].

In practice, engineering-geological zoning related to various types of construction has been studied by a wide range of researchers. Among the most notable contributions are those by F.P. Savarensky, I.V. Popov, V.D. Lomtadze, F.V. Kotlov, E.M. Sergeev, V.T. Trofimov, and others.

These researchers conducted studies on engineering-geological conditions followed by zoning of areas such as the East European Platform, West Siberian Plate, Siberian Platform, and many others. In Central Asia, notable research has been conducted on the engineering-geological zoning of the territory of Uzbekistan, major cities, and hydrotechnical structures by scholars such as G.A. Mavlyanov, S.M. Kasymov, A.M. Khudoyberganov, A.I. Islamov, M.Sh. Shermatov, G.Kh. Umarova, L. Goncharova, V. Kolpakov, and others.

Based on the analysis of stock materials and a literature review, it can be stated that until the 1930s-1950s, the main provisions of engineering-geological mapping were considered in the works of V.I. Popov, E.M. Sergeev, G.A. Golodkovskaya, V.V. Tolokonnikov, A.I. Islamov, G.A. Sulakshina, V.T. Trofimov, and G.A. Koff. Until the 1960s-1970s, relevant questions included the stability of the geological environment against anthropogenic impacts (E.M. Sergeev, G.A. Golodkovskaya, F.V. Kotlov, V.T. Trofimov, G.K. Bondarik, A.D. Zhigalin, etc.).

The analysis of the study of geocology, the natural environment, and engineering-geological conditions of the Karakalpak Ustyurt was addressed in the works of G.A. Mavlyanov, V.V. Tolokonnikov, V.F. Moskovets, G.F. Tetyukhin, A.I. Islamov, N.G. Mavlyanov, B.D. Abdullaev, A.V. Kleymenov, I.E. Kleymenova, P.R. Reymov, V.I. Sokolov, R.P. Aimuratov, R.K. Pirjanova, M.M. Zakirov, K.M. Dzhaksymuratov, and others.

Based on the above, it can be stated that for the Karakalpak Ustyurt, the issue of evaluating the state of engineering-geological conditions and engineering-geological zoning by the degree of resistance to anthropogenic impacts remains underexplored. For this region, the resolution of this problem is at the initial stage of its development. Different researchers interpret this concept in different ways. There is no full consensus on the methodology and principles of engineering-geological zoning according to the degree of resistance of the geological environment to anthropogenic impacts.

On the territory of the Karakalpak Ustyurt, a powerful factor of anthropogenic impact is both subsoil use and the development of mineral resources. Their impact on the environment, in terms of scale, exceeds the limits of individual investment blocks and influences the state of the ecological conditions of the studied area. Geological exploration and the development of mineral resources have a destructive impact on the environment, particularly on the geological aspect, related to the replanning of the relief, disruption of soil and vegetation cover, alteration of surface runoff and infiltration conditions due to the construction of drilling sites, laying of communications, and the construction of sludge ponds for drilling fluids and industrial effluents.

In addition to the aforementioned, dangerous geological processes during the zoning of territories are determined by the complexity of natural conditions and remain relevant for many years. Therefore, engineering-geological zoning based on topography and climate is an important tool for understanding the natural conditions of a region and using them in various fields. This work will contribute to determining the need for additional studies on soil and identifying potential risks associated with engineering-geological processes.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY. During the conducted engineering-geological studies of the studied territory, one of the most widely used systems of single-row (sequential) zoning was applied.

The degree of difference between the selected territories when creating engineering-geological zoning maps varies according to the complexity of the engineering-geological conditions. The main scale of the zoning map of the studied territory was 1:200,000, in which territories (zones) and sites were highlighted. [8]. In the multi-factor geological system of the southern part of the Karakalpak Ustyurt, zones with common taxonomic characteristics were identified, such as structural-geological composition. A site refers to the upper part of the cross-section of one geological formation and the characteristics of ongoing engineering-geological processes. [7,8].

During the engineering-geological survey, areas with identical or similar structural-geological, hydrogeological, and engineering-geological characteristics were mapped. Zones were identified based on parameters such as geological structure (uplifts, depressions, basins, and sagging), while sites were classified by soil type, groundwater depth, level of risk of geological and engineering-geological processes, etc.

It is important to note that the regional factors include neo-tectonic processes, while the zonal factors include geological and potential engineering-geological processes.

The degree of resistance to anthropogenic (technogenic) impact of each site was determined based on a complex of the natural ecosystem's ability to withstand anthropogenic (technogenic) loads that disrupt their natural functioning.

High resistance (3 points) corresponds to solid rocks (shell limestones, marls) up to 40 meters thick, arid, with a low or completely absent groundwater level (more than 30 meters), flat surface with weak or moderate intensity of modern geological processes, and relative stability of the area in a neotectonic context.

Medium resistance (2 points) is characterized by solid and medium-strength rocks (limestones, clayey-marls) with thicknesses over 10-25 meters, a shallow groundwater level (up to 25 meters), within a flat relief with the predominance of negative surface deformations.

Low and very low resistance (1 point) of geosystems is characterized by weak soils (aeolian sands, loams, saline soils, chemogenic deposits), the appearance of groundwater after floods in surface deposits, significantly dissected terrain, widespread and high-intensity modern geological processes.

For a quantitative assessment of the territory's susceptibility to karst manifestations, the following indicators were used:

- Density of karst sinkholes in the area:

$$f = \frac{N}{F}, \text{ units/km}^2$$

where N is the number of karst sinkholes, and F is the area of the studied territory;

- Karst coverage coefficient:

$$K_s = \left(\frac{F_k}{F} \right) \times 100 (\%)$$

where F_k is the area occupied by karst manifestations, and F is the area of the studied territory.

It should be noted that for certain areas, studies were conducted to quantitatively assess the territory's susceptibility to karst manifestations.

Thus, the studies were conducted according to the methodology for creating a map of engineering-geological zoning based on resistance to technogenic impacts.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. The basis of our engineering-geological zoning was the formation principle, taking into account the zonality of the distribution of stratigraphic-lithological complexes of rock formations (Fig. 1).

Four districts and 10 sites were identified (sites were selected based on the predominance of one of the engineering-geological factors). The degree of stability of the identified engineering-geological conditions of the site was determined based on the complexity of the engineering-geological conditions [5] and the following main factors: the type of soil cover, surface slope, depth of groundwater occurrence, protection of groundwater from contamination, presence of modern geological and engineering-geological processes and phenomena. The qualitative and quantitative characteristics of these factors were divided into three groups, to which points were assigned based on the degree of stability, corresponding to a three-point system (high stability – 3 points, medium – 2 points, and low – 1 point).

Fig. 1. Schematic map of the engineering-geological zoning of the Southern part of the Karakalpak Ustyurt region: taxonomic units of the districts are described below in the text (compiled by A.P. Akimova, G.E. Ochilov, 2024).

District A. This district is located in the northwest of the republic and covers the central and southern parts of the Karakalpak Ustyurt. Structurally, the district is part of the epigeric platform with the development of gentle and wide uplift zones. The district covers areas of the core foundation rocks and several local structures are identified: the Karabaur Ridge, the Aibogir Uplift, the Kaplanqir Plateau, and the Kaplanqir Chink (the latter partially extends into the territory of the Karakalpak Ustyurt). The section includes deposits from the Cretaceous, Paleogene, and Neogene. This district is divided into two sections.

Section A-1. This section is represented by Senonian marls with minor thin layers of clayey sandstones, and in the lower part of the section, dolomitized limestones. The terrigenous-carbonate formation consists of clayey-marley deposits from the Eocene. The lithological composition is

predominantly carbonate rocks, mostly marls. The rocks are gray, dark gray, brownish-gray, dense, rarely medium-density, slightly bituminous with layers of aleurites. The strength limit ranges from 85.9 to 243.0 MPa, and the bulk density is 2.6–2.64 g/cm³. The degree of resistance to anthropogenic impacts is 2 points with an increment of seismic intensity based on engineering-geological analogy, -1. The section is fragmented in geomorphological terms and is unfavorable for construction development.

Section A-2. This section is represented by a complex of marl-limestone rocks from the Miocene age. The lower part of the section consists of limestones with layers of marls, rarely clays, gypsum, and sandstones. The limestones are represented by shell limestones of gray color, porous, fissured, cavernous, and homogeneous in chemical composition. Initial stages of gully formations are observed in the section. Eluvial products of weathering semi-rock mountain formations are widespread. The compressive strength limits range from 0.24 to 1.67 MPa. The degree of resistance to anthropogenic impacts is 2 points with an increment of seismic intensity based on engineering-geological analogy, -1. Overall, the complex relief of both sections makes the district difficult to develop, and construction conditions are limitedly favorable, associated with numerous volumes of work. Furthermore, the section belongs to the 3rd complexity category according to engineering-geological conditions.

District B. This district is represented by deposits of the Miocene Sarmatian stage in the southern Ustyurt, spread along the slopes between the Central Ustyurt and Tuarkyr Kaplanqir uplifts. Geomorphologically, this district belongs to the South Ustyurt depression, its margins complicated by local uplifts. In the central part, it borders the Aksakeaudan-Sarykamysh depression. The northern margin of the depression adjacent to the Central Ustyurt Ridge is complicated by Shakhpakhte Step, which is separated from the more submerged part of the depression by a flexural-fault zone. The northern part of the Central Ustyurt (Karabaur) Ridge is almost completely covered by eluvial-deluviative formations, a product of weathering of the core Cretaceous and Neogene mountain rocks. On the southern slope of the Karabaur Ridge, non-fragmented Neogene-Quaternary deposits are limitedly distributed. At the same time, Paleogene deposits are assigned to the terrigenous-carbonate formation, Neogene deposits to the carbonate formation, and Quaternary deposits to the desert formation. Overall, this district has two sections.

Section B-1. This section is represented by the Sarmatian stage of Neogene deposits. The lower part of the section consists of gypsum-bearing clayey-marly deposits with a thickness of up to 40 m, while the upper part consists of limestones with layers of gypsum-bearing marls and clays, with a thickness of up to 80 m.

The water-bearing capacity of the Sarmatian deposits is not uniform: in structurally elevated areas, they are fully drained. The bulk density ranges from 2.0 to 2.17 g/cm³, and the compressive strength varies from 0.54 to 1.87 MPa. The degree of resistance to anthropogenic impact is 3 points with an increment of seismic intensity based on engineering-geological analogy, 0. Geological processes and phenomena, such as weathering, karst, and aeolian processes, are widely developed. Engineering-geological conditions here are generally favorable, except for the narrow strip of slopes adjacent to the Central Ustyurt and Tuarkyr Kaplanqir uplifts, where gully formation and partial landslides are common. Additionally, karst processes are widely developed in the limestones. These are expressed in the research area by the density of karst funnels, which range from 10-12 funnels per 1 km². Moreover, new and rejuvenated karst forms are observed, such as sinkholes, blind gullies, and pitted depressions.

Section B-2. Quaternary deposits, which have a relatively small thickness ranging from a few meters to 35-40 m, overlie older deposits. These are almost entirely non-water-bearing and constitute the upper part of the aeration zone. They are represented by layers of gypsum-bearing loams and sandy loams with inclusions of shell fragments and marls. The bulk density is 1.65 g/cm³, and the density is 2.3 g/cm³. The material composition of these deposits has not been studied. Weathering and salt formation in the aeration zone are widespread in this section.

Like Section B-1, the engineering-geological conditions here are generally favorable, except for the narrow strip of slopes adjacent to the Central Ustyurt and Tuarkyr Kaplanqir uplifts, where gully formation and partial landslides are common. Also, as in Section B-1, karst processes are less developed here, with a funnel density of 8-15 karst funnels per 1 km². Special attention should be paid to studying the development of hazardous geological processes when developing the site. The degree of resistance to anthropogenic impact is 3 points with an increment of seismic intensity based on engineering-geological analogy, 0.

Region V. This region belongs to the area of lake-accumulative plains, which occupies extensive depressions and their marginal areas. These plains formed during the Quaternary period and are characterized by accumulative landforms that originated in the presence of water bodies. On the current relief background, the low-lying areas are associated with the Barsakelmes and Assakeaudan depressions. They are the largest depressions, with steep, cliff-like slopes, some of which reach heights from 10 to 40 meters. The predominant deposits here are modern-Quaternary. The extensive bottom of the Assakeaudan depression has a gently rolling relief. In both depressions, hilly sands are widespread—distinct accumulations of sandy-clay material near shrubbery. The Assakeaudan depression stretches nearly 80 km in an east-west direction. Additionally, only on large dry valleys along the southern slopes of the Karabaur Valley are Quaternary alluvial deposits found. The lake-accumulative plains are represented within the inner part of the sinkhole and the Sarykamysk Lake. There are four terrace steps in the direction of the lake from the sinkhole, with terrace heights ranging from 0.5 to 1.25 meters. The area is covered with shrubs and dried algae. Throughout the region, there are second- and third-stage gully formations. The first stage involves the formation of a rill or rut, with depths ranging from 0.30–0.50 meters to 1.5 meters. Due to stream erosion, triangular depressions are observed, extending for several dozen meters. The second and third stages of gully formation are widespread, with a step formed by temporary streams. In all cases, the mouth of the step is above the erosion base, and the gully depth can reach 10–30 meters. The absence of vegetation on the gully slopes indicates the ongoing development of the process. All gullies have a V-shape, with steep, cliff-like, exposed slopes affected by slope gravitational processes.

Section V-1. This section is represented by loams, fragments of marls and clays. Further down the profile, there are layers of gravel, loam, and fine-grained sand, with poorly rounded pebbles and plates of gypsum and halite salts. The degree of resistance to anthropogenic impact is 1 point, with an increment of seismic intensity based on engineering-geological analogy, +1.

Section V-2. This section is primarily represented by modern Quaternary alluvial deposits in the form of poorly rounded pebbles of various sizes. The pebbles mostly consist of limestone, marl, and clayey-marl rock fragments. These deposits are strongly saline, with gypsum and halite salts predominantly present as powders and crystals. The maximum size of the takyr (salt flats) in the area reaches up to 1.5 km². The complicating factor for development in this area is the hazardous geological processes, including bed and lateral erosion, landslides, gully formation, and

salinization. The engineering-geological conditions of this section are generally unfavorable. The degree of resistance to anthropogenic impact is 1 point, with an increment of seismic intensity based on engineering-geological analogy, +1. The territory is complicated for development due to dangerous geological processes, including bed and lateral erosion, landslides, gully formation, and salinization. The engineering-geological conditions of the section are generally unfavorable.

Section V-3. This section is represented by loams, medium and fine-grained sands. On the terraces of the upper parts of the lake-accumulative relief, there are layers of weathered calcareous-marly pebbles, with sizes ranging from 1.0 to 2.5 cm, cemented by gypsum and halite salts. The thickness of these layers ranges from 0.5 to 0.75 meters. The degree of resistance to anthropogenic impact is 1 point, with an increment of seismic intensity based on engineering-geological analogy, +1. The engineering-geological conditions of this section are favorable for the construction of modern structures, such as "Sardoba" reservoirs, and for providing drinking water for pasture farming and other human activities on the site.

Section V-4. This section is represented by a complex of lake-chemical saline deposits of modern Quaternary age. It forms the bottom of the depression and is primarily composed of common salt. The deposits are contaminated with black silt, a product of erosion from the depression's slopes due to seasonal atmospheric precipitation and the draining of groundwater in the depression area. The thickness of these deposits ranges from 2.0 to 10.0 meters. The degree of resistance to anthropogenic impact is 1 point, with an increment of seismic intensity based on engineering-geological analogy, +1. The engineering-geological conditions of this section are generally unfavorable for construction.

Region G. This region covers the area of the inner and outer sinkholes, with varying widths determined by the influence of processes affecting the state of the sinkhole itself, i.e., neotectonic movements. In addition, canyons and gullies are commonly observed. Apart from the inner and outer sinkholes, weakened zones are widespread, where displacements of Neogene limestone layers along Palaeogene marls and clays are observed. Gullies are found as short segments ranging from 0.8 to 1.5 km, depending on the geomorphological conditions, rock composition, and slope characteristics.

Section G-1. In the sinkhole of the plateau, light gray layered marls and limestones with shell fragments are commonly observed. These rocks are fissured, porous, cavernous, and chemically homogeneous. Further down the profile, they also appear fissured, with cracks filled with powdered and crystalline gypsum and covered with halite on top. Throughout the area, the rocks are subject to weathering, fissure formation, and landslides. The degree of resistance to anthropogenic impact is 1 point, with an increment of seismic intensity based on engineering-geological analogy, +1. The engineering-geological conditions of this section are unfavorable for construction.

Section G-2. This section is represented by a complex of developing processes that contribute to the formation of canyons, gullies, and karst cavities. The distribution of the section across the studied area is located along the northern flank of the Akseaudan depression, the eastern slopes of Barsakelmes, and some sections of the inner sinkhole of Ustyurt. At the foot of the sinkhole and the slopes of the depressions, mass accumulations, landslides, and collapses have formed, and gullies have started here, cutting through the sinkholes and ridges, forming canyons with vertical walls ranging from 10 to 20 meters. The degree of resistance to anthropogenic impact is 1 point, with an increment of seismic intensity based on engineering-geological analogy, +1.

The territory is complicated for development due to hazardous geological processes. The engineering-geological conditions of this section are generally unfavorable.

CONCLUSION. Thus, the analysis of the current state of engineering-geological conditions and the geological environment in the southern part of the Karakalpak Ustyurt has been conducted in order to create a schematic map of engineering-geological zoning based on resistance to anthropogenic impacts. The study area is characterized by widespread slope gravitational processes and various engineering-geological conditions. These conditions, influenced by climatic factors and neotectonic movements, result in the activation of processes such as weathering, gully formation, and certain gravitational processes in the areas of the inner and outer sinkholes.

The engineering-geological zoning of the southern part of the Karakalpak Ustyurt is based on a formation principle that takes into account the zonality of the distribution of stratigraphic and lithological complexes of rock formations.

The following regions were identified:

- **Region A:** Structurally, this region represents part of the epigeric platform with the development of gentle and broad uplift zones (Karabaur Uval, Aibogir Uplift, Kaplanqyr Plateau, and Kaplanqyr Chinck).
- **Region B:** Represented by Miocene Sarmatian deposits spread on the slopes of the Central Ustyurt and Tuarkyr Kaplanqyr Uplifts.
- **Region C:** This region is part of the lake-accumulative plains, covering vast depressions such as Assakeaudan, Sorja, and the northwestern edge of Barsakelmes.
- **Region D:** Covers the area of the inner (escarpments in the eastern part of the Barsakelmes depression and the western part of Lake Sarykamysh) and outer (eastern part of the Ustyurt Plateau) sinkholes, with varying widths.

A total of 10 sections were distinguished, based on the predominance of a particular engineering-geological factor. Additionally, the degree of resistance to anthropogenic impacts and the increase in seismic intensity, depending on the engineering-geological conditions of the selected sections, were determined. In conclusion, the research conducted will actively contribute to the preservation of the natural environment and to geological exploration activities. An important aspect is that the schematic map of engineering-geological zoning will be used to justify local construction projects and regional planning for linear structures (such as roads, railways, and oil and gas pipelines).

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